

LANGUAGE LEARNING AND PSYCHOLOGY

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ELSEVIER

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Abstract: As learning a second language is harder than learning other topics, it is crucial to motivate students when teaching them. This is where psychology comes into play when learning a foreign language. Therefore, we can draw the conclusion that teaching a young child a foreign language is really beneficial for their growth. The teaching strategies employed during the session have an impact on the language proficiency of the students. The teacher must therefore be aware of the pupils' skills and English proficiency level. Understanding that a child's proficiency in a foreign language depends on their age aids a teacher in creating an effective teaching strategy and an engaging lesson. The group determines the children's degree of English proficiency.

Keywords: psychology, language learner, self-esteem, motivation, teaching, psychological education.

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Educational psychology is a fundamental knowledge for teachers to help students improve their knowledge. It does not matter whether the teacher teaches English at school or university during English lessons. In reality, teaching as a second/foreign language is a difficult task. When a pedagogue with excellent educational psychology leads the classroom, he can be more successful in teaching than other teachers. First, the teacher tries to create motivation in the class and attract the student's attention to the topic. Lack of motivation is the main obstacle to the student's academic achievements, so all the efforts of the teacher are aimed at eliminating them. obstacles and encourage the class to learn more. The use of visual aids in teaching English creates a strong motivation between the second/foreign language learners and the context, which makes it easier for them to learn new words in the acquired language and helps them to remember them forever. Motivation as an energizing need or desire drives behavior and can be classified as such. As Wilkins points out, "motivation is a term that arises not in learning a first language but in discussing a second language." There are two types of motivation: Intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Socio-cognitive motivation can also be defined as integrative motivation and instrumental motivation (Gardner, 1960). Instrumental motivation refers to the desire to learn a foreign language in order to find a job or to improve oneself or improve one's social status (Dörnyei, 2009). Second, a skilled teacher reduces a student's stress and anxiety, and builds self-esteem. Sometimes students have learning difficulties,

which lowers their self-esteem. Inadequate self-esteem makes them accept positive thoughts, resulting in poor performance. Thus, the teacher should be able to find the root of this fear and stress and help the students overcome them through appropriate strategies. Most students are afraid to speak in English class, because they think they will be ridiculed by their classmates if they say something wrong, including using wrong words or pronouncing words incorrectly. According to psychologists, the role of the pedagogue in this case is important, in which the teacher focuses on the class and prevents any anxiety, and also patiently corrects his mistakes. Education expert Dr. Muhammad Reza Dehrangi said, "In today's world, the term teaching is not used. It is accepted as the task of the teacher, but today's students need to be encouraged to reach a mature frame of reference, and this is done by developing this framework independently".

In fact, the teacher is not the absolute leader in the classroom, but the leader. The understanding of individual differences of students and their recognition in the work of teachers is very important, and the needs of different students and the teacher can discover and understand the different abilities of students and help them. Thus, teachers with a background in psychology patiently and creatively help their students without worrying about helping their students succeed.

In general, teaching in an English class is an in-depth and planned activity and specific objectives designed to be achieved by the teacher. To be successful in teaching, the teacher must have the necessary information and knowledge such as new educational theories and educational psychology.

Teachers must first be good psychologists. In the teaching process, focusing on the learner's role in the teaching process and its reinforcement can be effective in language learning. teaching them how to teach English. Logical education and principles are one of the effective factors of the teaching process.

It is known that in teaching a foreign language, organizing the educational process taking into account the age characteristics of students is considered a guarantee of success. First of all, the task set before the student should be suitable for their abilities, that is, it should not be too difficult for the student. In the course of psychology, it is known that students (in the middle stage of learning a foreign language) grow up quickly, as a result, they get tired quickly, get angry quickly, and become stubborn. Therefore, it is considered appropriate to replace the active activities of language learning in the 4th-5th grades with work that does not require much activity. This is especially important at the end of the lesson. The 7-8th grade foreign language class is distinguished by the thematic and intensive study of language material. At this stage, students do not like to act and stand still (without any task). Therefore, the theme of the foreign language lesson in the 6th-7th grade should not be weakened at all. According to some scientific works, by the 8th

grade, students' ability to remember foreign language material (of different content) increases, (not literal recall, but observational memory) his interest fades. Many students are bored in class and do not show activity, they are indifferent to the task. If students of this age do not have enough self-control, and their internal dissatisfaction, quick temper, and resistance are strong, this leads to a decrease in interest in foreign languages. They lose confidence in their own strength and abilities. This does not affect the educational process, one of the reasons for the decrease in interest in studying is the disproportion of the students' general activity and activity to the student's requirements. For example: in 4-5th grade, confidence, natural desire to learn language, grade norms and do what adults say, etc. k. If we measure the age characteristics of 4th-5th graders and 6th-7th graders, it becomes clear that reading is important for 4th-5th graders. Speaking in a foreign language for 6-7 graders. Students of this age have a strong desire for independence and self-management.

Sometimes, putting one's self against the whole class and showing oneself, one's identity in front of others, some children have a strong desire to show their abilities in front of other children. It is here that children think about their future and become interested in a profession. All of the above makes it difficult to teach a foreign language and control students' activities. To prevent this, it is necessary to carry out special work. That is, it is necessary to help them to satisfy their desire for independence, to make it the right way. Aggressiveness is especially strong among 7-8 graders. As a result of being strict with them, increasing control, increasing their aggressiveness, various conflicts arise between the student and the teacher. Therefore it is suggested to relax the demands a little, to exclude competition from the elements that cause tension in the educational process. At this age, the most important thing is to succeed in one's activities (at work, at home, in studies). Therefore, the foreign language teacher should show the students' small achievements in learning a foreign language. Embarrassing the student for his mistake in front of his peers causes disrespect towards the teacher and a sense of revenge. 7-8th grade students try to compare themselves to others, regardless of the type of activity, and they want to achieve superiority in this. This desire in them is manifested when they endure various difficulties, try to show their willpower, and strive to win over fear. They have a strong desire to show their "identity". At the middle stage of foreign language teaching, we should organize the educational process taking into account the uniqueness of the psychological and physiological qualities discussed above. It seems to the students that the material of the language they are learning is fully understood before, but this mistake will not be repeated after a certain time, it will not be kept in memory and it will not be an active composition. The material is said to be mastered only if it is repeated. (10-20%

increase in recall). Explanation: active learning: passive learning: external learning is stronger than internal learning for intermediate students, so it is necessary to use both learning methods wisely.

The exercises and the tasks set before the students should have a problematic movement, they should be a stimulus to induce intellectual emotion. It is necessary to conduct the lesson based on the principle of communicativeness, and it is important that each speech activity originates from a realistic situation. Let students enjoy their success in speaking a foreign language. 7th-8th graders don't even try to speak a foreign language because they don't want to be laughed at because they speak a foreign language too well. The failure of foreign language teaching at this intermediate stage is due to the psychological adaptation of the educational process to a fake situation. It is known that speech in their native language is rich in information. Their foreign language speech is primitive and not ready to express the students' wishes. Therefore, it is necessary to use situations arising from real events in the lesson, to conduct various games in the lesson. But it is not possible to use the games that are typical for 4-5th grade, because the 7th-8th grader is afraid of being laughed at by his classmates. At such a time, the most important thing is to use the types of games performed with a positive attitude in different roles. Children of this age should be widely involved in extracurricular activities. Unfortunately, in many cases this is not done in schools. In addition, the communication between the teacher and the student in a foreign language plays a big role. The age of students of 9-10th grade is characterized by a number of psychological features by the beginning of adolescence. The uniqueness of their young characteristics begins to form from the 8th grade. It is known from the course of psychology that some of the features of the age from the previous stage are preserved in each age stage. Adolescence is a period of formation and maturation of a person. At this age, adolescents develop the characteristics of attitude to the external environment and evaluation of their own activities. But at the same time, it is characteristic of teenagers to overestimate their strength and show their individuality. This often causes various difficulties. There is a significant change in the students' memory, their attitude to the subjects of study, and the subject of a foreign language.

For example: at the beginning of the 7-8th grade, the interest in learning a foreign language fades. But by the 9th-10th grade, students look at learning a foreign language with a special interest and responsibility. Due to the change in the psychology of students at this stage, they may not perform well in the previous stages. High school students perform exercises with no clear purpose without interest and indifference. But they read semantically related texts with special interest. At this stage, independent work plays a special role, especially with a

foreign language. The requirements for classes in the upper grades are different from those in the previous stages. Now the lesson is not based on oral speech, because at this stage most of the language material is learned passively (receptively). That is, reading comprehension plays a key role. Texts are also complex in terms of size and large language material. The organization of the lesson on a complex basis should alternate with the study of some aspects of the language material (lexical and grammatical) in some cases. One of the difficulties of teaching a foreign language at this stage is the reduction of class hours. Oral speech skills are acquired only in class, therefore, due to the limitation of class time in upper classes, we have to preserve and improve the skills and competences previously achieved in the field of dialogic and monologic speech. Pupils should conduct a conversation in class about the events that interest them in the life of our country and England. It is necessary to pay attention to the development of listening comprehension skills. At this stage, in addition to learning to read quickly, students should learn to use the vocabulary of a foreign language and their native language. The skills of learning to understand from the context also start from this stage, so it is allowed to have some unfamiliar words in the texts. Reading practice is carried out on the basis of texts that do not refer to a light dictionary.

In conclusion, not only foreign language but all science teachers should be able to be a good psychologist at the same time as a teacher. We studied the main plans of this topic as follows:

Subjects and tasks of the science of psychophysiology, that is, we got an understanding of the goals and tasks of the science of psychology. Before understanding the psychology of foreign language learners, we need to understand what psychophysiology is.

The psychology of foreign language learners, as everyone knows, the most alternative way to master not only language, but other subjects is to study the human character and take this into account. It is much easier to learn the language based on studying human psychology.

The importance of psychology in learning a foreign language, we know that mastering a second language is more difficult than other subjects, and in this case it is very important to teach by motivating the student. In addition, we can conclude that learning a foreign language at preschool age is very useful for the child's development. Students' achievement in foreign language is related to the methods used during the lesson. Therefore, it is important for the teacher to know the students' abilities and current level of English. Knowing that children's ability in a foreign language depends on their age helps the teacher to make an effective teaching plan, to make the lesson interesting and effective. Children's level of knowledge of English depends on the group and the child himself. However,

trying to use more complex methods to teach students with low English proficiency can lead to a lack of understanding in the group and, consequently, a lack of motivation. It is very important for the teacher to use different teaching methods and to be able to adapt the curriculum according to the age and foreign language level of the children.

REFERENCES:

1. Abdullayeva, G. (2021). Personality factors as one of the main issues influencing language learning. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 6(6).
2. Abdullayeva, G. (2022). LEARNERS' PSYCHOLOGY AS ONE OF THE MAIN ISSUES INFLUENCING LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 11(11).
3. Deci, Edward L., and Richard M. Ryan. "The" what" and" why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior." *Psychological inquiry* 11, no. 4 (2000): 227-268.
4. Dornyei, L. (2009). Motivation in second and foreign language learning. *Language Teaching*, 31(3), 117-135.
5. Gardner, R.C. Motivational Variables in Second-Language Acquisition. Thesis submitted for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy. McGill University 196
6. Kobilova Aziza Bakhriddinovna. Semantic and lingua-cultural features of English and Uzbek medical periphrases // *International Journal on Integrated Education*. ISSN (Online): 2620-3502, Vol.5, Issue 6, 6-June 2022. P. 162-167. <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJIE/article/view/3144>